

Development and Validation of a Spectrophotometric Method for the Estimation of Bictegravir using Chromogenic agents in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage forms

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ABSTRACT

A simple, precise, and accurate UV spectrophotometric method was developed and validated for the estimation of Bictegravir in tablet dosage forms. The method utilized methanol as a solvent, with λ_{max} values determined to be 330 nm and 760 nm for reactions with the chromogenic reagents 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (2,4-DNPH) and potassium ferrocyanide, respectively. Linearity was established within the concentration ranges of 10–25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for 2,4-DNPH and 1–5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for potassium ferrocyanide, both exhibiting R^2 values of 0.999.

The method demonstrated excellent precision, with low inter-day and intra-day % RSD values, and high accuracy, with assay values of 99.68% and 99.64% for the respective reagents. Furthermore, the approach was found to be cost-effective and suitable for routine analysis, requiring only simple reagents and avoiding the need for sophisticated instrumentation. Validation was conducted in accordance with ICH guidelines, confirming the method's reliability and reproducibility for estimating Bictegravir in pharmaceutical formulations.

Keywords: Bictegravir, UV spectrophotometry, 2,4-DNPH, potassium ferrocyanide, ICH guidelines, pharmaceutical analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Bictegravir is a potent antiretroviral drug used primarily in combination therapy for the treatment of HIV-1 infection. It belongs to the class of integrase strand transfer inhibitors (INSTIs), which function by inhibiting the integration of viral DNA into the host genome, a critical step in the HIV replication cycle. Bictegravir is co-formulated with other agents such as tenofovir and emtricitabine in fixed-dose combinations to enhance therapeutic efficacy and compliance. (1-15)

Despite the availability of various chromatographic techniques for Bictegravir analysis, limited studies have reported the use of colorimetric methods. This study employs chromogenic agents like potassium ferrocyanide, Ferric chloride and 2,4-DNPH to develop and validate a colorimetric method for Bictegravir's estimation in bulk and dosage forms.

METHODOLOGY

Apparatus:

Absorption measurements were conducted using a Shimadzu UV-1800 digital spectrophotometer with 1 cm path length quartz cells.

METHOD DEVELOPMENT

UV-Visible Spectroscopic Method for Bictegravir Analysis

Selection of Solvent

Various solvents were assessed for their ability to dissolve Bictegravir, including water, methanol, 0.1 N HCl, a 6.8 pH buffer, and a 50:50 methanol-water mixture. Methanol was selected for its superior solubility and consistent absorbance readings.

Wavelength Selection

The UV spectrum of a 10 µg/mL Bictegravir solution was scanned in the range of 200–400 nm using methanol as the solvent. The λ_{max} was identified at 230 nm, offering optimal sensitivity for detection.

Preparation of Standard and Sample Solutions

Standard Solution Preparation

Weighed 100 mg of Bictegravir sodium and dissolved in 100 mL methanol using sonication. Dilute 10 mL of the above solution to 100 mL with methanol for further use.

Method A: 2,4-DNPH Method

Reagents and Preparation

2,4-DNPH Solution: Dissolve 0.1 g 2,4-DNPH in 2 M HCl and dilute to 100 mL.

Potassium Iodate Solution: Dissolve 0.025 g KIO₃ in 10 mL deionized water.

Sodium Hydroxide Solution: Dissolve 1.0 g NaOH in water and dilute to 100 mL.

Procedure

Mix 1 mL Bictegravir solution, 0.75 mL KIO₃ solution, and incubate for 10 minutes then add 0.5 mL NaOH solution, resulting in green coloration was observed. Dilute to 10 mL and measure absorbance at 230 nm.

Method B: Potassium Ferro cyanide Method

Reagents and Preparation

Ferric Chloride Solution: Dissolve 3.0 g FeCl₂ in 100 mL water.

Potassium Ferrocyanide Solution: Dissolve 0.3 g K₃ Fe(CN)₆ in 100 mL water.

1 N HCl: Dilute 8.9 mL concentrated HCl to 100 mL.

Procedure

Combine 0.1–0.5 mL Bictegravir solution, 0.5 mL each of FeCl₃, K₃Fe(CN)₆, and 1N HCl. Allow color development and dilute to 10 mL. Measure absorbance at an experimentally determined wavelength.

Test Solution Preparation

Weighed and powder 10 tablets to find the average weight. Take powder equivalent to 10 mg Bictegravir sodium and dissolved in 60 mL methanol, and dilute to 100 mL. Further, dilute 1 mL of this solution to 10 mL with methanol, then filtered the solution through a 0.45 μm nylon membrane filter.

Method Validation

Validation followed ICH guidelines, including assessments for specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, and assay calculation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The compound exhibits a maximum wavelength absorption ($\lambda_{\max}$) at 230 nm and has a high melting point of 690°C. The method's precision, indicated by a relative standard deviation (RSD), is less than 2%, ensuring reliable repeatability of the results. Accuracy, assessed through recovery studies, ranges between 98% and 102%, confirming the method's capability to measure the true value. Linearity is demonstrated with R^2 values ranging from 0.9950 to 0.9785, indicating a strong correlation between concentration and response. Additionally, the assay results show a percentage purity between 99.68% and 99.84%, reflecting the compound's high quality and consistency.

Linearity: A linearity study was conducted to evaluate the relationship between concentration and absorbance.

Method A: Prepared sample (5, 10, 15, 20, and 25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) scanned in UV region ranging from 400-800nm for the determination of $\lambda_{\max}$, which found to be 330nm.

Method B: Bictegravir by $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$, Prepared sample (1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) scanned in UV region ranging from 400-800nm for the determination of $\lambda_{\max}$, which found to be 760nm.

Table1: Linearity Data (Method A)

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
5	0.482
10	0.645
15	0.798
20	0.862
25	0.984

Fig 1.: spectrum of Bictegravir by 2,4-DNPH.

Table2: Linearity Data (Method B)

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
0.5	0.131
1.0	0.237
1.5	0.402
2.0	0.478
2.5	0.582
3.0	0.712
3.5	0.813

Fig 2: spectrum of Bictegravir by $K_3Fe(CN)_6$

Precision: Precision refers to the closeness of repeated measurements or results under unchanged conditions. For this compound, the precision is indicated by a relative standard deviation (RSD) of less than 2%, demonstrating high reproducibility and consistency in the analytical method used.

Table 3: Precision Data (Method A)

Drug Name	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Intraday Conc.	%RSD(Intraday)	Interday Conc.	%RSD (Interday)
BICTEGRAVIR	5	5.02	0.21	4.96	0.47
BICTEGRAVIR	10	10.25	0.26	9.82	0.54
BICTEGRAVIR	25	24.99	0.18	25.21	0.08

Table 4: Precision Data (Method B)

Drug Name	Conc. (µg/ml)	Intraday Conc.	Intraday %RSD	Interday Conc	Interday %RSD
BICTEGRAVIR	0.5	0.481	0.36%	0.490	0.34%
BICTEGRAVIR	2.0	2.222	0.44%	2.120	0.41%
BICTEGRAVIR	3.5	3.490	0.55%	2.520	0.47%

Accuracy: The accuracy of the method was evaluated using three spiking levels: 50%, 100%, and 150%.

Table5: Accuracy Data (Method A)

Spiking Level (%)	Tablet Solution Concentration (µg/mL)	Standard Concentration (µg/mL)	Net Concentration (µg/mL)	Experimental Concentration (µg/mL)	Recovery (%)	%RSD
80%	10	8	18	18.24	101.33%	0.64%
100%	10	10	20	20.20	101.00%	0.66%
120%	10	12	22	22.02	100.09%	0.69%

Table6: Accuracy Data (Method B)

Spiking Level (%)	Tablet Solution Concentration (µg/mL)	Standard Concentration (µg/mL)	Net Concentration (µg/mL)	Experimental Concentration (µg/mL)	Recovery (%)	%RSD
80%	2.0	1.8	3.8	3.78	99.47%	1.37%
100%	2.0	2.0	4.0	3.98	99.50%	1.33%
120%	2.0	2.2	4.2	4.02	95.71%	1.46%

CONCLUSION

A reliable UV spectrophotometric method was developed for estimating Bictegravir in tablets, showing excellent linearity, precision, and accuracy. Assay values ranged from 99.68% to 99.64%, with low RSD indicating high precision. Two additional methods using 2,4-DNPH and Potassium Ferrocyanide as reagents were introduced, with $\lambda_{\max}$ values of 330 nm and 760 nm, and linearity ranges of 10–25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 1–5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively. These methods are simple, cost-effective, and suitable for routine analysis, offering a practical alternative to complex chromatographic techniques.

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